

The Role of Negation in Verbal Morph Synthesizer for English-Oriya Machine Translation System

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Abstract:

One of the core activities to increase the quality of the machine translation Output is Morphological synthesizer. This paper describes the feature based sentential agreement, Negative particles synthesis with Verb inflectional or derivational morphology. This mentioned computational model is being designed to automatically extract the contextual features, to make an agreement with negative particles and try to synthesize for the generation of effective and possible vocabulary creation in Oriya Language. Here we followed rule based affix binding methods and feature based derivation morpheme identification to make an agreement with possible negation particles.

Keywords: Natural language generation (NLG), Negation, Machine Translation (MT), Modal auxiliary

1. Introduction

Human languages have means to overtly "deny the truth of a proposition"(Dahl 1993:914)ⁱ is a great contemporary linguistic phenomenon, has attracted most researchers to analyze the 'negation' in much deeper level. In agglutinative languages like 'Oriya' Morphological synthesis is an essential part of any natural language generation system. Oriya is a highly inflectional language is very dependent on the feature and syllable structure of the root respectively. In Oriya Negation verbal morphology synthesis, the synthesis engine selects the appropriate suffixes, prefixes, infixes etc, determines the ordering among them and concatenates them according to the rules and agreement. Looking to this nature of constraints, here we try to describe the architecture of a Negation verbal morphology synthesis system based on spot feature recognition.

2. Negation in Oriya Language:

Generally the negative markers in any language are trying to convert the meaning of the verb to its exact opposite. In Oriya there are a number of negative markers available such as: nAM, nAhiM, ni, nuheM, na, nuhaM, nAhAnti, anu etc. When these negative particles are added to the verb of Oriya language mostly by Sandhi rules, there is no structural change noticeable and as such they are simply an addition where by the meaning of the verb is changed from infirmity to negativity.

3. Constraints on Word Order and Negation:

3.1 Verb & Negation

In Simple Verbs (verbs are made up of one single verb root) the Negation takes place just after the verbal derived morph as a suffix by changing whole or part of the derived morph or infixes itself agreeing with the derived morph in between verb root and derived morph.

rAma bahi padhinAhiM (Ram has not read the book.)

rAma bahi padhini (Ram has not read the book.)

In the above two sentences, the negation marker ‘nAhiM’ and ‘ni’ takes the suffix position of the verb root ‘padhibA’ (read) and replaces its affirmative derived morph feature ‘achi’ and synthesized to make the derivation as ‘padhinAhiM’ and ‘padhini’ respectively. However in the sentences like:

rAma kichhi kahilA nAhiM (Ram didn’t talk anything.)

rAma kichhi kahilAni (Ram didn’t talk anything.)

Here the negation markers one form ‘nAhiM’ in past perfect tense sense only replaces the corresponding derivational morpheme but not synthesized itself. However the second one both replaces the derivational morpheme and synthesized itself. However in the sentences ‘Rama bahi padhinathilA’ (Ram hadn’t read the book.), the negation marker ‘na’ in modified form without changing the verbal derivational morpheme insert itself within them. So the above description allow us to draw the inference that Verb and Negation forms in Oriya language are inseparable cluster in which internal order is free.

3.2 Participle or Relative Clause Verb and Negation:

In Embedded Participle or Relative Clause Verb, the Negation particles either infixes or prefixes the derived morpheme or the verb root participle form. In the sentence, ‘rAma pDhinthibA/napaDhithibA bahiTl mora The book not read by ram is mine.’ the form, ‘pDhinthibA’ or ‘napaDhithibA’ are possible.

3.3 Infinitive & Negation:

In Conjunct Verb Group (made up of different parts of speech) case the Negation would take place just before the Auxiliary Modified verbal part rather than the main expression. Ex: In ‘manjuri nadebAku’ (not to-approve), the Negation takes place just before the ‘debA’ not the before of ‘manjuri’. i.e. ‘namanjuri debAku’ would make the construction rather effective. However; in Simple Verbs (verbs are made up of one single verb root) the Negation would take place just before the verb root rather the just before of

Auxiliary. Ex: napaDhibAku (not to read) is possible. In reverse paDhinaBAku would make the grammatical construction wrong.

4. Functional Classification of Negation:

4.1 Negation as a verb: In English, the Negation at Copulative case not makes the distinction itself. In contrast, the negation in Oriya language it replaces itself the place of Copulative position. In English Sentence, Ex: She isn't a girl. (In this case 'n't' associate itself with the verb 'is' not affecting the grammatical (Tense, Number, Person, Gender) identity. However in Oriya language sentence 'Se goTiE bALikA nuhem.' the word 'nuhem' itself replace the corresponding affirmative value and takes the grammatical identity on its own as [Simple, Copulative, III-Person, Singular, and Non-Honorific].

Similarly, the sense of possession, the copulative verb like 'achhi, etc.' in the addition of negation also receives the same respect (nAhim) as above in Oriya language.

4.2 Negation as a prefix: the Oriya Modal auxiliary particles expressing the sense 'Obligation' most cases take the place as a prefix of its obligation explanatory marker. Ex: Apana E kAma karibA anuchit. Here the Negation marker 'an' synthesized with the obligatory marker 'uchit' makes the popular word 'anuchit' rather than the form like 'uchit nuheM'.

4.3 Negation as Ellipsis: When an Auxiliary appears alone omitting a main verb, but is understood is treated as ellipsis. In the sentence "Mu kataka jibi, kintu se nuheM." the negation 'nuheM' takes the notion of the previous verb 'jib' and a spice of negation and represents the whole meaning.

5. Negation Synthesizing Process:

Different methods have been evolved for the development of an effective morph synthesizer. Especially for agglutinative languages like Oriya, we have here considered the synthesizing process very specific to the affix binding methods. Here the case of negation, we have tried to describe the process of Verb synthesis process with inclusion of Oriya negative particles. At the instant level, we find the Verb root category by the Suffix stripping method as its searching process is relatively first. Again in our empirical observation, it is confirmed that root belonging to the same Template behaves in the same way under morphological operation and the structure of the verb root follow the method of regular expression for both inflectional and derivational morph synthesis. The details of the synthesizing process are at the fig no. 1.1.

Fig No. 1.1 Negation Morph Synthesizer for English-Oriya MT System

In this synthesizing process, we club the negation adverb notion ‘n’ available in target text to the Verb Phrase as it is mostly agreed with Verb root and morpheme in Oriya language. So from Verb phrase our method at first distinctly separates the Negation (N), Verb Root (V) and probable morphemes (X). The Verb root enters into the Verb feature Identifier where its selection of Template Category and the probable transitivity happens. However, the Probable Morpheme ‘X’ enters into the Aux-Verb Scanner.

Here ‘X’ = {∅, m, a}. Where ‘X’ may be null or any available source language morphemes ‘m’ and available aux ‘a’.

The Aux-Verb Scanner looking to the input string ‘X’ would determine the TAM feature (Tense, Aspect, and Modality), which would be an input for our ‘VM Decision Maker’. The ‘VM Decision Maker’ collecting the template value and transitivity of ‘V’, taking the subject feature ‘f’ and making a coordination with our Verbal Morpheme Bank decides the value of ‘X’ as ‘x’ which would be the agreed target Verbal Morpheme. In Negation Morph synthesizing process all ‘n, V and x’ are considered as the input value to determine the synthesized derived value as ‘V’.

In automation process the Synthesizing Agreement module looking to the value of ‘n, V and x’ decides the exact position of ‘n’ among V and x’. Where ‘n’ may be a prefix, suffix or an infix. Or it may complete replace the value of verbal morpheme and takes the predefined value.

The process of appending the suffixes (x’) to the verb root is not trivial in Oriya language; that is where the information of the template name of the verb is required. Depending on the template, there are changes that take place at the boundary and at the internal structure of the root while concatenation. The rules for the handling the changes during the concatenation process are picked from the respective template row values matching with n and x’. A typical rule for concatenation is on the form

$V' \longrightarrow n (nAhiM) + V^* + x'(karichhi) \longrightarrow V^*karinAhiM$

Here ‘*’ is the template name and the negation value ‘nAhiM’ replaces the value of ‘chhi’ from x’ and forms the V’ as V*karinAhiM.

In same if the MT system in pre-synthesize level provides the value of the sentence ‘Tourists take buses not to move ahead.’ As ‘Agaku *nuheM jibA ku* basaguDika NEbE’, then its negation verb synthesized value by applying Negation-Infinitive Morph synthesized value as ‘Agaku *najibAku* basaguDika nebe’.

Conclusion:

This paper has tried to describe some novel approaches for Oriya Morphological synthesis specially taking the consideration of Negations. With this, there are some contextual behaviors of Negation markers and how their ordering makes the difference in syntax and semantic nature of the Oriya language are also explained. Again the negation except the Copulative and possessive sense, how in other cases it affects the time variables and tense marker of Oriya language are in research.

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